

PROCEDURES FOR AWARDING WITH THE HONORARY LABEL OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

Jasurbek Karimjonov

Faculty of History of the National University of Uzbekistan

Teacher of the newest history department of Uzbekistan

[*expert0almazniy@gmail.com*](mailto:expert0almazniy@gmail.com)

ANNOTATION

In this scientific article, about the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which is important in encouraging worthy services of citizens to the state and people in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the contribution of those who have been awarded this award to the development of the country's economic, social, and cultural spheres. explained through the basics. Also, special attention was paid to the description of this established Honorary Label, to whom it is awarded, for what services, awarding procedures, award money, and statistics of those awarded over the years.

***Key words:** state award, Republic of Uzbekistan, honorary label, statute, awarding.*

INTRODUCTION. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a system of awarding citizens, organizations and institutions, as well as citizens of foreign countries, with state awards has been established. In addition to orders and medals, awarding processes are being carried out with the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan. . On December 17, 2009, a law was adopted on the approval of the regulations on the honorary label of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the description of the honorary label of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan are awarded with the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan for their labor and combat services, effective state, social and creative activities. Persons who are not citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan may be awarded the Order of Honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Along with citizens, enterprises, institutions, organizations, public associations, creative teams and military units, as well as administrative-territorial units can also be awarded with the Medal of Honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Persons awarded with the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan receive a one-time monetary award in the amount of five times the base calculation amount or a souvenir of the same value. In the case of a posthumous

award of the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the monetary award will be handed over to the family of the awardee.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Methods and methods such as objectivity, truthfulness, idealism, patriotism, historicity, statistical comparative analysis are used in this scientific article. Given that it is related to the period of independence and that it is being researched for the first time, information on the subject is recorded mainly in periodicals and collections of laws.

RESULTS. The badge of honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan consists of a form placed in a folder of the specified model. The volume consists of a 252.5 x 340 mm frame. At the top of the page is the state coat of arms. In the center below the coat of arms, there are two lines, the words "Republic of Uzbekistan" are written in the first line, and the words "Degree of Honor" are written in the second line. From the lower edge of the left page, on the background of Huma bird and sunlight, a part of the Arch of Virtue installed in Independence Square - storks flying over the globe, symbols of creativity and peace, are depicted. On the right page, horizontally in the center, from the upper edge, the standard of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan is depicted. On the left and right sides of the standard, the State flag of the Republic of Uzbekistan is displayed in the same way. On the lower edge of the standard of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the text "For effective contribution to the development of our country and active participation in social and political life" is located in dark blue on the background of huma bird and sun rays. Two lines are drawn from the bottom line of the text to record the surname, first name and patronymic of the awardee. Centered vertically from the bottom line, the text is in three lines. In the first line, the words "of the Republic of Uzbekistan" are written in dark blue color, in the second line, in bronze-low color, "Honorary label", in the third line, in dark blue color, the words "Awarded with" are written. On the lower left side of the page, the text "President of the Republic of Uzbekistan" is located in two lines, on the right side, symmetrically, the first letter and last name of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan are located. Two lines are drawn from the lower edge of the page to record the award date and the serial number of the Honorary Label of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1.].

DISCUSSION. After independence we can see that many awards related to this award have been done. Initially, 16 employees of the Republican Matlubot Cooperation were awarded with the honorary badge of the Republic of Uzbekistan[2.6-7.]. It can be seen that most of the 137 awardees from the field of mechanical engineering on September 27, 1991 were employees of the Chkalov Aviation Association[2.8-13.]. According to the decree of October 25, 1991, 66 employees of automobile transport were awarded for many years of honest work and achievements in production. The awardees consist mainly of drivers, repairmen, and

machinists. This was also the first state award received by the representatives of this field after independence [2.21-23.]. By the decree of November 9, 1991, a group of representatives of the fish industry of Karakalpakstan, Tashkent, Fergana and Bukhara regions, as well as a group of neighborhood committee activists were awarded, and all of them are the chairman of the neighborhood. On November 21, 1991, for the first time, employees of the Ferghana State Pharmacy were awarded with an honorary label and an honorary title[3.14.]. On December 4, 1991, a group of military personnel of the Nevel unit (Termiz) with the Order of the Red Banner twice was awarded for their active service. This was a decree on awarding the first soldiers after independence. Also, 18 representatives of the field of geology - prospecting were awarded with this award [4.100.]. Most of the members of a certain team were awarded with a certificate of honor, but in some cases we can see that one person was also awarded separately. For example, Bernora Qoriyeva, chairwoman of the Union of Theater Actors of Uzbekistan, was specially awarded with this award for her many years of creative work and services in the development of Uzbek national ballet and dance[5.10.].

On March 24, 1992, 473 employees of the Republican Agricultural-Industrial Complex were awarded in the regions. On August 28, 1992, Presidential Decree PF-463 was adopted on the largest award for this year. On the occasion of the first anniversary of the declaration of independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1005 citizens were awarded in the region and 415 citizens in the sector. The social structure of the awardees was diverse and consisted of representatives of state administration, production, industry, science, culture, law and order and other fields[7.8-64.]. Individuals, citizens, enterprises, institutions, as well as administrative regions were awarded state awards. For example, on August 31, 1992, for the achievements of the President in the development of the national economy, for successfully solving tasks in the social, household and cultural spheres, the Zadaryo district of the Namangan region was awarded the medal of honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which was the first award after independence. is an administrative territorial unit[8.78.]. Also, the city of Nukus of the Republic of Karakalpakstan was awarded with a certificate of honor for its achievements in the field of economic and cultural construction, on the occasion of the 60th anniversary of its establishment [9.20.]. In addition, 122 citizens from various fields were awarded on the occasion of the first anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution. This was considered the biggest awarding event of this year[10.7-16.]. Studying the presidential decrees on awarding honorary titles, it became clear that a separate decree was adopted mainly for regional governors or the first heads of state agencies. A decree was passed on awarding many teams operating in a certain field.

On February 17, 1994, the Metallurgical Plant of Uzbekistan [11.6.], on September 26, 1994, the Institute of Medical Rehabilitation and Physiotherapy named after N.A. Semashko was awarded, and state institutions and organizations were also awarded from the above opinion [12.54 -55.].

On May 26, 1994, a group of participants of the Days of the Republic of Kazakhstan will be awarded in Uzbekistan. According to it, 4 meritorious artists, 2 meritorious cultural workers and 14 persons will be awarded Honorary Certificates from the participants from Kazakhstan. This was one of the first cases of awarding citizens of a foreign country by the Republic of Uzbekistan [13.19-20.].

On March 5, 1994, a group of women from 38 republics was decorated for the first time after independence in connection with the development of the economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan, promotion of science and culture, special services in educating the young generation, and International Women's Day on March 8. Although women were awarded before this decree, this decree is significant because it aims to reward a group of women of the republic [14.20-23.].

In 2001, the joint-stock company "Ukraine-Uzbekistan Trade House" was awarded for its contribution to the strengthening of friendship and solidarity between the peoples of Uzbekistan and Ukraine, and the development of mutual economic relations[15.219.].

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, in the first years of the state's declaration of independence, taking into account the fact that the awarding system was not yet fully formed, and the orders and medals were not established, it can be said that the badge of honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan was widely used to motivate citizens. In general, representatives of the industry, working in production, service, science, culture and other fields, are awarded for their meritorious services.

REFERENCES

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the approval of the regulations on the badge of honor and the description of the badge of honor of the Republic of Uzbekistan <https://lex.uz/docs/1560390>
2. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1991. No. 12. - P. 6-7.
3. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 1. - P.14.
4. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 2. - P. 100.
5. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 5. - P.10.
6. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 6. - P.5-22.

7. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 11. - P. 8-64.
8. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1992. No. 10. - P.78.
9. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1993. No. 2. - P. 20.
10. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1993. No. 11-12. - P.7-16.
11. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1994. No. 3. - P.6.
12. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1994. No. 10. - P.54-55.
13. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1994. No. 6. - P. 19-20.
14. Bulletin of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 1994. No. 3. - P.20-23.
15. Bulletin of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan, 2001. No. 9-10. - P.219.